

Do environmental regulations induce environmentally reactive firms to act? Evidence from the Indian context

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Abstract

In their efforts to bring sustainability into the mainstream, countries across the world are enacting various environmental regulations. However, are these regulations and the resultant regulatory institutionalisation actually inducing environmentally reactive firms to act? We seek to address this question by exploiting a quasi-experimental setup—the enactment of the National Green Tribunal Act 2010 in India. We theorise that environmental regulations induce environmentally reactive firms to make significant changes to their value creation process, thereby affecting their process-based indicators and by extension, their financial performance. Our work has the potential to contribute to two streams of literature. First, it may extend neo-institutional theory by identifying conditions wherein coercive pressures may yield the intended results. Second, our work might add to the literature on Porter's hypothesis by providing evidence of increased innovation offsets in the case of environmentally reactive firms that leverage low-hanging fruits such as eco-efficiency.

Keywords

Environmental regulation, regulatory institutionalisation, environmental proactivity, mainstreaming sustainability, difference-in-difference